
Gender Equality Plan

for the R&I field in the Region of Central Macedonia

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Region of Central Macedonia

South East European Centre - SEERC

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FOREWORD / MESSAGE FROM THE AUTHORITY OF THE REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA (Greek)

Η Ισότητα των Φύλων αποτελεί θεμελιώδες ανθρώπινο δικαίωμα και βασικό στοιχείο κάθε σύγχρονης δημοκρατικής χώρας γι' αυτό και η ένταξη της Διάστασης του Φύλου στο σύνολο των πολιτικών των σύγχρονων κοινωνιών (gender mainstreaming) αποτελεί πλέον προτεραιότητα. Σύμφωνα με την Έκθεση Ισότητας των Φύλων της Ευρωπαϊκής Κοινωνικής Επιτροπής, οι γυναίκες ακόμα και σήμερα εξακολουθούν να αποτελούν την πλειοψηφία των οικονομικά ανενεργών ατόμων, να είναι πιο ευάλωτες στη φτώχεια, τον κοινωνικό αποκλεισμό και τη βία και να αντιμετωπίζουν ακόμα μεγαλύτερες οικονομικές δυσχέρειες.

Στον τομέα της Έρευνας και Καινοτομίας παρατηρείται χαμηλή εκπροσώπηση των γυναικών στις Φυσικές Επιστήμες, την Τεχνολογία, την Επιστήμη των Μηχανικών και τα Μαθηματικά και ειδικότερα στα υψηλότερα επίπεδα διαχείρισης της Έρευνας & Καινοτομίας στην Ακαδημία και στη Βιομηχανία.

Στη σημερινή συγκυρία είναι, ίσως περισσότερο από ποτέ, είναι επιβεβλημένη η ένταξη της Διάστασης του Φύλου σε όλες τις πολιτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα διοίκησης (κεντρικό, περιφερειακό, τοπικό) και σε όλες τις εκφάνσεις της οικονομικής, κοινωνικής και πολιτικής ζωής. Κατά συνέπεια, πρωταρχικό μέλημα μας ως Επιτροπής Ισότητας των Φύλων της Περιφέρειας Κεντρικής Μακεδονίας είναι η ανάδειξη όλων των προβλημάτων που αντιμετωπίζουν οι γυναίκες και η εξεύρεση λύσεων, η ευαισθητοποίηση και ενημέρωση της κοινωνίας και η εξασφάλιση των προϋποθέσεων για την επίτευξη της Ισότητας των Φύλων στην Ελληνική Κοινωνία.

Μέσα από την χαρτογράφηση των αναγκών του οικοσυστήματος Έρευνας και Καινοτομίας και τη διαρκή συνεργασία με τα ερευνητικά και ακαδημαϊκά ιδρύματα της Περιφέρειας μας, τους θεσμικούς φορείς και τις επιχειρήσεις που δραστηριοποιούνται στην Έρευνα και στην Καινοτομία καθώς και την Κοινωνία των Πολιτών συνδημιουργήθηκε το παρόν **Σχέδιο Ισότητας των Φύλων (ΣΙΦ)**.

Το συγκεκριμένο Σχέδιο Ισότητας αποτελεί ένα χρήσιμο μεθοδολογικό εργαλείο, που μπορεί να προσαρμοστεί στις ανάγκες του κάθε φορέα, ώστε κατά τον σχεδιασμό, την εφαρμογή και την αξιολόγηση των πολιτικών του, να λαμβάνονται υπόψη όλες οι απαραίτητες παράμετροι για την επιτυχή ενσωμάτωσή τους και την εφαρμογή πρακτικών που θα αποσκοπούν στην ουσιαστική Ισότητα των Φύλων.

Η Πρόεδρος της Επιτροπής Ισότητας Φύλων στην ΠΚΜ

Σοφία Μαυρίδου

Αντιπεριφερειάρχης ΠΕ Πιερίας

Glossary of gender-related terms

(European Institute of Gender Equality-EIGE, Glossary & Thesaurus)

Disadvantaged groups: Groups of persons that experience a higher risk of poverty, social exclusion, discrimination and violence than the general population, including, but not limited to, ethnic minorities, migrants, people with disabilities, isolated elderly people and children.

Diversity: Differences in the values, attitudes, cultural perspective, beliefs, ethnic background, sexual orientation, gender identity, skills, knowledge and life experiences of each individual in any group of people.

Equal access to resources for women and men: Concept implying that both women and men have equal access to, use of and benefit from all specific resources (material, financial, human, social, political, etc.).

Equal opportunities for women and men: Absence of barriers to economic, political and social participation on grounds of sex and gender.

Equal treatment of women and men: a state of no direct or indirect discrimination based on sex and gender, including less favourable treatment of women for reasons of pregnancy and maternity.

Gender: Social attributes and opportunities associated with being female and male and to the relationships between women and men and girls and boys, as well as to the relations between women and those between men.

Gender awareness-raising: Process that aims at showing how existing values and norms influence our picture of reality, perpetuate stereotypes and support mechanisms (re) producing inequality.

Gender bias: Prejudiced actions or thoughts based on the gender-based perception that women are not equal to men in rights and dignity.

Gender blindness: Failure to recognise that the roles and responsibilities of women/girls and men/ boys are ascribed to, or imposed upon, them in specific social, cultural, economic and political contexts.

Gender dimension (or perspective): Ways in which the situation and needs of, and challenges facing, women and men (and girls and boys) differ, with a view to eliminating inequalities and avoiding their perpetuation, as well as to promoting gender equality within a particular policy, programme or procedure.

Gender equality: Equal rights, responsibilities and opportunities of women and men and girls and boys.

Gender equality competence: Skills, attributes and behaviours that people need in order to mainstream gender concerns effectively into policies and plans and help build gender equality.

Gender Equality Plans (GEPs): a set of actions with different degrees of complexity meant to articulate a strategic view aimed at achieving gender equality.

Gender gap: Gap in any area between women and men in terms of their levels of participation, access, rights, remuneration or benefits.

Gender identity: Each person's deeply felt internal and individual experience of gender, which may or may not correspond to the sex assigned at birth.

Gender mainstreaming: Systematic consideration of the differences between the conditions, situations and needs of women and men in all policies and actions.

Gender norms: Standards and expectations to which women and men generally conform, within a range that defines a particular society, culture and community at that point

in time.

Gender quotas: Gender-balanced participation and representation by establishing a defined proportion (percentage) or number of places or seats to be filled by, or allocated to, women and/or men.

Gender stereotypes: Preconceived ideas whereby females and males are arbitrarily assigned characteristics and roles determined and limited by their gender.

Gender-neutral language: Language that is not gender-specific and which considers people in general, with no reference to women and men.

Gender-sensitive: Policies and programmes taking into account the particularities pertaining to the lives of both women and men, while aiming to eliminate inequalities and promote gender equality.

Glass ceiling: Artificial impediments and invisible barriers that militate against women's access to top decision-making and managerial positions in an organisation.

Horizontal segregation: Concentration of women and men in different sectors and occupations.

Intersectionality: The ways in which sex and gender intersect with other personal characteristics/identities (e.g. race, religion, social status), and how these intersections contribute to unique experiences of discrimination.

Irregular and/or precarious employment: Various forms of non-standard, atypical, alternative employment.

Non-sexist language: Avoidance of ambiguous generic masculine gender in the grammatical forms of nouns and discriminatory expressions.

Parental leave: Leave granted to either parent in order to care for a child.

Sex: Biological and physiological characteristics that define humans as female or male.

Sexism: Actions or attitudes that discriminate against people based solely on their sex and/or gender.

Sexual harassment: any form of unwanted verbal, non-verbal or physical conduct of a sexual nature occurs, with the purpose or effect of violating the dignity of a person, in particular when creating an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating, offensive environment.

Sticky floor: Expression used as a metaphor to point to a discriminatory employment pattern that keeps workers, mainly women, in the lower ranks of the job scale, with low mobility and invisible barriers to career advancement.

Structural inequality: Embedding gender inequalities in social structures, based on institutionalised gender conceptions.

Substantive gender equality: Combination of formal gender equality with equality of outcome, meaning that equality in law, equal opportunities and equal treatment of women and men are complemented by equality in impact, outcome or result.

Vertical segregation: Concentration of women and men in different grades, levels of responsibility or positions.

Women's triple role: Reproductive, productive and community managing role.

Work-life balance: Achieving balance between not only domestic tasks and caring for dependent relatives, but also extracurricular responsibilities or other important life priorities.

1

Introduction

1.1 State-of-the-art of Gender Equality provisions in Europe

1.2 State-of-the-art of Gender Equality Provisions in Greece

1.1 State-of-the-art of Gender Equality provisions in Europe

Gender equality, as defined in accordance to the humanitarian perspective and individuals' welfare and to the Humanitarian-Development Divide (United Nations Sustainable Development Goals – SDGs and Priority of Gender Equality by UNESCO), is a key aspiration of contemporary societies at a universal scale. It is seemingly one of the key aspirations of the European Community, as evidently argued in the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and in the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union:

“The enjoyment of the rights and freedoms set forth in this Convention shall be secured without discrimination on any ground such as sex, race, colour, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, association with a national minority, property, birth or other status.”

(Article 14 – Prohibition of discrimination, Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms)

“In all its activities, the Union shall aim to eliminate inequalities, and to promote equality, between men and women.”

(Article 8 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union)

Following the same line of argument, the European Commission (EC) argues in favour of gender equality and equity and proceeds to relevant well-structured policies and strategies particularly in the field of Research &

1.1 State-of-the-art of Gender Equality provisions in Europe

Innovation (R&I) and with reference to the European Research Area (ERA). Two of the most recent (and major) gender-related strategies publicly communicated in the European Union are a) the “Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 - A Union of Equality” (EC, 2020); b) the “Position paper on the gender equality priority in the European Research Area 2020-2030” (further enhancing the 2020-2025 strategy), developed by the ERAC Standing Working Group on Gender in R&I (EU, 2020). According to the position paper, gender mainstreaming in the R&I field and in the ERA roadmap should be structured around 8 specific points/recommendations across the years 2020-2030 (Table 1).

- ▶ Gender equality conceptualised as intersecting with other factors, such as age, health status, disability, occupation, socioeconomic status, migratory status, and geographic location (intersectionality) must remain a priority in the future European Research Area.

- ▶ The institutional change approach must remain the core principle for reforming all ERA institutions.

- ▶ An integrated approach to effective framework conditions for gender equality in research and innovation must be enhanced.

- ▶ The structures for gender equality in R&I at the national and EU level must continue and be reinforced.

- ▶ Responsible national authorities must be held accountable.

- ▶ The policy design, monitoring and evaluation system must be revised and reinforced.

- ▶ Equality should be linked with funding.

- ▶ Gender must be mainstreamed in all future priorities of the ERA (in line with the Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 and the intersectional gender perspective).

Table 1. The 8 recommendations for gender mainstreaming in R&I in the years 2020-2030.

Finally, the EC proceeds to well-structured and multilayered initiatives for gender mainstreaming and for enhancing gender equality in the R&I field (and corresponding organizations) through various funding programmes. Considerable initiatives are evolved (and have been evolved in the past years) indicatively within the funding programmes of Framework Programme 7 and Horizon 2020 (for more information see the section Further resources). As for the upcoming funding programme of Horizon Europe (2021-2027), the

1.1 State-of-the-art of Gender Equality provisions in Europe

EC indicates that Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) will be an eligibility criterion for research organisations, higher education institutions and public bodies. This eligibility criterion will be applicable from 2022 onwards, and the aforementioned organisations must have a gender equality plan in place, fulfilling mandatory process-related requirements. The mandatory GEP process requirements refer to:

- A public document (formal document, signed by top management, published on the institution's website, disseminated through the institution)
- Dedicates resources (funding for gender equality positions or teams, reserved time for others to work on gender equality)
- Data collection and monitoring (data on sex or gender of staff across roles and leadership, annual reports and evaluation of progress and outcomes)
- Training and capacity-building (engagement on behalf of the entire organisation, tackling gender biases of people and decisions, joint action on specific topics).

Additional to these, the EC has recommended some areas that the GEPs should address, in the sense that these areas cover some essential factors for gender equality in R&I. These refer to:

- Work-life balance and organisational culture
- Gender balance in leadership and decision-making
- Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
- Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content
- Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

1.2 State-of-the-art of Gender Equality Provisions in Greece

Following the European perspective and line of action, the Greek community has acknowledged the value of gender equality as a core principle at a national level. Based on the Greek Constitution (2001) (ΦΕΚ 85/A/18-4-2001):

“Greek men and Greek women have the same rights and obligations.”
(Article 4, par. 2)

“Taking positive steps to promote equality between men and women does not constitute gender discrimination. The State accommodates to eliminate the inequalities that exist in practice, particularly to the detriment of women.”
(Article 116, par. 2)

Emphasis should also be placed on LAW No. 4604 according to which, the State’s core aim is described as “Promoting substantive Gender Equality, Preventing and Combating Gender-Based Violence – [providing] Provisions for Granting Citizenship -Provisions for Elections of Local Authorities- Other Provisions” (for more info, see the section Further resources).

Proceeding a step further, the General Secretariat for Gender Equality (GSGE) has been appointed by the Hellenic Parliament as responsible for the design and implementation of national equality policies for the elimination of gender discrimination, as well as for and the overall promotion of gender equality. Its policies evolve around four core axes, namely: promoting female em-

1.2 State-of-the-art of Gender Equality Provisions in Greece

ployment and addressing the equality gap in the labour market; preventing and combating violence against women; addressing stereotypic perceptions about the roles of the sexes and genders through educational procedures; reinforcing women's participation in decision-making centres. The most recent National Gender Equality Action Plan was released by GSGE (2017) with reference to the years 2016-2020, and encompassed 6 basic principles – target areas (Table 2).

▶ Social inclusion and equal treatment of females being recipients of multiple discriminations.

▶ Gender-based violence.

▶ Labour market, harmonisation of professional and family life.

▶ Education, Vocational Training, Culture, Sports and Media.

▶ Health.

▶ Equal female participation in power/high-authority structures, processes and decision-making bodies.

▶ (Horizontal legislative interventions).

Table 2. The basic principles-target areas of the National (Greek) Gender Equality Action Plan (2016-2020).

With reference, finally, to the Greek R&I field (or R&D – Research and Development), no tailored frameworks or policy lines have been outlined as in the case of the European Research Area. The EU and National policies primarily encompass the Greek R&I field and, secondarily, it is up to R&I actors and organizations to pursue the application of the national policies (e.g. establishment of Gender Equality Committees in Higher Education Institutions), or even develop more tailored lines on action. Some more precise indications for the Greek context can be retrieved from the Report of the “Pissaridis Committee” (2020) on the Development plan for the Greek economy. Along these lines, emphasis has been placed on addressing the unequal provision of opportunities for females in the labour market. It is argued that companies should enhance the concept of social responsibility and consequently support females during maternity leaves (p. 152), by considering this time period as a standard part of their career rather than an obstacle. Intersectionality and the rights of disadvantaged/minority groups should seemingly be considered for battling against discriminations (p. 155).

2

Strategic context of the Gender Equality Plan

- 2.1 Gender Imbalances in the European and Greek R&I field
- 2.2 The objectives of the RCM Gender Equality Plan in R&I
- 2.3 Implementation of the regional GEP

2.1 Gender Imbalances in the European and Greek R&I field

Irrespective of the various provisions in both Europe and Greece, gender imbalances remain a prominent challenge in various spheres, including the professional, economic, social or political one. Research and Innovation (R&I) is one of the core fields exhibiting a constant gender gap, manifesting itself in various forms. Indicatively¹, with reference to doctoral graduates, female representation is almost equal to the male one (47.9% in 2016 in the EU-28). There is, however, a considerable under-representation in specific fields and mostly in the STEM-oriented ones; women constituted 68% in the field of Education, and only 21% in Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and 29% in Engineering, Manufacturing and Construction in 2016 (EU-28). Proceeding to inequalities in the labour market, these become more evident while approaching power or high-authority positions, which are ‘typically’ dominated by males and intensify/reinforce the “glass ceiling” or “sticky floor” effect. In the EU-28, the female proportion of R&D personnel working as researchers in the higher education, government and business enterprise sectors is lower than the corresponding male proportion in most countries; on the contrary, the situation for working as other supporting staff is reversed. As an additional and general remark to Science and Technology (S&T)

1. The statistics about gender representation in R&I in Europe and Greece have been retrieved from the publication *She figures 2018* (European Commission) and from the publication *Women’s participation in Research and Innovation in Greece* (National Documentation Centre, 2020).

occupations, tertiary educated women in Europe are generally more likely to be unemployed than tertiary educated men, while the EU country assembling the highest percentage on this type of unemployment for women is Greece (18.6% in 2017).

Since, however, gender (in)equality is not just a numerical problem calculated only in statistical percentages in R&I positions, it is seemingly worth highlighting some imbalances in working conditions (e.g. mode of employment, type of contract etc.) and particularly for researchers. In most EU countries, more women are working part-time when compared to men (13% as opposed to 8% in EU-28 in 2016), while female researchers in the higher education sector tend to work under precarious agreements more often than men in 2/3 of the EU countries. Finally, while at the early stages of their career (e.g. during a PhD) female and male researchers are equally mobile, men seem to maintain higher mobility rates during the middle or senior career stages (3.6% difference at EU level, irrespective of an increase in female mobility rates during the years 2012-2016).

The situation and the gender gap in the R&I field in Greece moves across the same lines as in the European context. The pool of female doctoral graduates in 2018 was statistically equal to the one of men (50% in 2018, as opposed to 46.2 % in 2016), but female representation remained weaker in Engineering and ICT fields (33.9% in 2018). The female academic staff representation in Greek Higher Education institutions then seemingly suggests considerable imbalances; female professors in Grade C reached 37.5% and in Grade A only 22.2% in 2017, thus adding evidence to the claim that the 'sticky floor' and the 'leaky pipeline' phenomena are considerably evident in the Academia. Equally important is finally the participation of female R&I staff in research projects. In the case of ERC grants² for the years 2014-2018, 22 Greek female researchers received funding (as opposed to 88 Greek male researchers).

As far as working conditions are concerned, precarious working agreements in Higher education sector are most often made with females rather than male researchers (8.1% as opposed to 1.7% in 2016). Some minor imbalances seemingly exist with reference to part-time employment (2.1% of women as opposed to 1% of men in 2016).

2. It is worth highlighting that out of the 104 individuals receiving ERC funding, 29 of them perform their research in Greek institutions. Out of them, only 5 are women.

2.2. The objectives of the RCM Gender Equality Plan in R&I

The Region of Central Macedonia recognizes the benefits of the R&I field for the economic and social development of the region. It consequently recognises that people in the R&I field are one of its most important assets; their capabilities, performance, working conditions and dedication are contributing to the mission of enhancing the progress of R&I in the region.

Concurrently, the Region's commitment to a dynamic and innovative vision further suggests that a culture of inclusion and diversity (based on EU and Greek national strategic lines) must be present in the R&I field and corresponding actors. The justification for that can be somehow characterized as twofold, owing to the urgent need to:

- 1) tangibly enhance universal principles and notions on equality, gender, inclusiveness, rights to diversity, and challenge manifestations of intersectionality through the R&I field;
- 2) further avoid the waste of talents due to gender gaps and imbalances, and address the prominent brain drain in the region (and consequently the region's progress).

Ultimately, it is this exact progressive bridging of gaps and inequalities that has the potential to reverse some prominent gender imbalances at a regional and national level, and also ensure a systematic progress towards a pan-European reality fostering equality and inclusion.

Based on the above rationale, the objectives and foci of the regional GEP have been shaped within the context of addressing gender-related challenges in R&I. These challenges are horizontally associated with the organizational structures and institutional image of the R&I organisation per se. Under a more vertical perspective, the challenges evolve around the entire course of an individual in the R&I fields and organisations, starting from the hiring procedures and provision of equal opportunities, and reaching up to working conditions and professional recognition in middle/senior career stages.

2.3 Implementation of the regional GEP

In order to set the basis for the operational implementation of the GEP, a step-by-step co-design procedure was primarily applied for ensuring that the Equality plan addresses 'true' gaps and challenges in the R&I field of RCM (along with the commonly accepted challenges at EU and National level). To meet this end, workshops and consultation meetings were organized with representatives and/or members of R&I organizations as well as with lay citizens, during the time period 2019-2021 (for more information on the participants of the workshops/consultation meetings and their valuable contribution, see the Acknowledgments).

Based on the data collected from 1) the mapping of the EU and National gender-related landscape; 2) the mapping of the regional R&I system; 3) the co-creation (co-design) meetings with regional stakeholders, the regional GEP for the R&I field is structured around eight strategic areas/areas of intervention. These areas attempt to tackle the most profound and gender-related challenges in R&I organisations, and each one of them assembles a list of indicative action points as a proper means to address the challenge per se. Similarly, these eight areas cover the recommended areas/essential factors for GEPs by the EC –thus providing to the R&I organisations of RCM a robust basis for developing their GEPs.

The action points and accompanying data (e.g. tools for implementation) are characterised as "indicative", since the core aspiration refers to the GEP functioning as a template for the R&I organizations of the Region. Each R&I organisation has its own structures, internal mechanisms and procedures, hence a regional GEP with doctrinal action points and suggestions cannot be considered as feasible. All data included in the section of Strategic areas (Strategic area 1 – Strategic Area 8) aim to serve as a basis and provide a framework for R&I organizations in RCM to develop their own GEP. In other words, they will be able to implement self-tailored effective strategies around workplace culture, leadership, and employment practices, thus tackling specific challenges within the context of their own institutions/workspaces and improving gender equality across the whole organisation.

Following the same line of argument, the monitoring indicators and evaluation criteria provided in this document are indicative as well. The organisations that will implement a GEP should consult these and employ them as a starting point / as an inspirational basis. The final indicators that will be employed by the various R&I organisations for monitoring and evaluation must be dependent on the action points adopted – thus a uniform monitoring framework is not feasible.

3

Strategic areas of the Gender Equality Plan

3.1 Description of strategic areas

3.1 Description of strategic areas

1. Female career progression³

An important step towards favouring gender equality in R&I refers to supporting women progress in their career tracks and maintain them after considerable career breaks. It is generally noticed that women seemingly face several barriers to promotion, and factors influencing both career progress and continuity vary from gender biases in recruitment procedures to the opportunities that the working environment provides (research grants, training, re-skilling etc.). Female career progression is then heavily reflected in and manifested through the leaky pipeline effect, the glass-ceiling effect and vertical segregation. There is yet considerable work to be done in acquiring a better understanding of the multi-layered barriers towards female career progression, as well as in developing a more equal reality where females a) advance in their careers without encountering gender-related obstacles; b) further claim positions of higher authority; c) challenge stereotypes about women not exhibiting the necessary capacities for high (scientific) positions (L'oreal Foundation Study, 2015). Strategic measures and institutional good practices are necessary for reaching this reality, without however overlooking the 'nature' of the measures favouring females in the workplace, –so as to avoid the perpetuation of gender stereotypes due to these measures (Oetke et al., 2016)

3. All the strategic areas of intervention will be accompanied by some corresponding monitoring indicators, once the lists of indicative action points are finalized.

Figure 1. The 8 strategic areas of the RCM GEP.

2. Gendered science

Gendered science considers sex and gender as scientific variables and suggests the incorporation of these two into scientific research, so as to further address gendered stereotypes in knowledge production. It has the potential to lead to new research protocols and new research agendas, which can capitalize on the following core concepts: gender-sensitive research, gender-transformative research, gender-aware science, gender-specific research (GENDER-NET EU project, 2016, D3.11). The Directorate-General for Research and Innovation of the European Commission has been highlighting the incorporation of the gender perspective in EU-funded programs, and defines as a prerequisite the description of how the gender perspective is considered within the context (and activities) of EU funded research projects (e.g. Horizon 2020 projects). The latest manifestation of this is the requirement that all academic entities participating in HORIZON EUROPE have a functional Gender Equality Plan from 2022 on.

3. Confronting Social and Cultural Stereotypes - Challenging horizontal segregation

Contemporary societies and R&I organizations in these societies should be committed to a culture and a working/learning environment that celebrates diversity and inclusion. Some social and cultural stereotypes or prejudices, however, still remain quite extended nowadays and often allude to the attribution of a male and female 'sign' in some professions, or to assumptions towards females not having the necessary capacities to enter the world of the so-called 'hard sciences', including STEM (L' Oréal Foundation study 2015; Miller, Eagly and Linn 2015). The intersectionality and the unconscious bias that are inherent in our society can further enrich such stereotypes and lead individuals to facing multiple barriers and disadvantages based on a variety of attributes and life experiences. Horizontal segregation can be a common obstacle that females will encounter in their working environment due to gender-based stereotypes, making it challenging (or intimidating) for them to enter R&I sectors and occupations that are typically 'male-dominated', i.e. the STEM-oriented ones.

4. Projection of female role models – appropriate scientific communication

In order to effectively address gender-based social and cultural stereotypes—and consequently both vertical and horizontal segregation—, female role models and the work or experiences of successful women in the R&I field (e.g. scientists, entrepreneurs) should be projected and communicated. It has been indicated that scientific communication highly affects the STEM-related engagement of females of all ages (Galdi, Cadinu and Tomasetto, 2014), while multiple 'examples' of role models should be projected in order to avoid the danger of sub-typing (Bigler and Liben, 2006; Park, Wolsko and Judd, 2001). During sub-typing, individuals view people who do not belong to a stereotype as disconfirming exceptions and deviant members of a group—in this case, due to the lack of appropriate and adequate in number examples, females who are heavily engaged in STEM and/or successful in the R&I field may be faced as 'odd' exceptions.

5. Gender-neutral (or gender-sensitive) Language in Institutional Communication and Dissemination

The linguistic structures that individuals employ reflect their thoughts and attitude, and key sociolinguists have argued on how text and talk can (re)produce relationships of dominance, discrimination and control (Fairclough 2013; Van Dijk 1994; Wodak 1989). The use of gender-marked or even sexist language within an organisation can thus create several implications, including: (unconscious) perpetuation of gender-based stereotypes, organizational practices hindering gender equality (operational level), projection of a prejudiced image for the institution (symbolic level). An institutional transformation in terms of language should therefore address both the internal level of the organisation referring to communication protocols, as well as the external level referring to the organisation's communication and dissemination activities towards its end-users.

6. Work-life balance

The necessary balance between work and family/personal life is a core dimension among the objectives of gender equality. Particularly parenthood evokes a new division of labour that inevitably places more responsibilities primarily on women –who tend to carry both the burden of professional obligations, with no relative decrease in the family-related ones (Duxbury and Higgins, 1994; O'Laughlin and Bischoff, 2005). As a consequent result, the conflict between new family responsibilities and professional obligations can lead to considerable career setbacks or breaks, and to the diversion from highly-valued career paths. Common examples refer to the disruption of scientific production and to converting from research-oriented work to teaching (within the academic context), or to abandoning administration for support positions and part-time employment. Ultimately, an R&I organisation enhancing work-life balance should aim at creating a flexible workplace that enables staff to balance work and life responsibilities.

7. Sexual harassment and gender-based violence

Both sexual harassment and gender-based violence in organisations and workplaces can create an intimidating, humiliating, offensive or hostile and harmful environment. As suggested by EIGE, both phenomena can evoke major costs and consequences, including: lost economic output, provision of services, including health, legal, social and specialised, as well as personal (physical and emotional) impact on the victim. Particularly with reference to sexual harassment cases, these are characterized by various degrees of severity, ranging from repeated invasion of personal space to sexual assault. Sexual assault can actually be characterised as an “advanced stage of harassment” and suggests that an organisation has failed to implement preventive measures (Bell et al, 2002, p. 16).

Such phenomena remain a considerable challenge both for Europe and Greece; indicatively, 60.2% females and 50.4 % males in Greece have suggested that sexual harassment is a fairly common phenomenon in the country (EIGE 2016 indicators). Based on the above indications, protection and support in R&I organisations towards individuals of all genders

(male, female, gender-neutral) and of all sexual orientations must be ensured. Sexual harassment is increasingly being seen as a management and leadership-related problem, and a proactive stance is seen as necessary (Hunt et al, 2010); as it has been put forward even thirty years ago, sexual harassment and gender-based violence should be considered as issues needed to be addressed by the organisation, rather than simply increasing and improving an individual's skills in order to deal with harassment (Fitzgerald and Shullman, 1993).

8. Raising awareness on gender issues

The final and horizontal strategic area refers to raising awareness towards gender issues within the R&I organisations' environment. It is merely not enough to only implement GEPs and related measures within an organization, since there is a genuine need to stimulate comprehension and sensitivity towards the nature of gender equality and towards organisational and societal aspects penetrated by gender norms and values. Awareness can be raised and information can be provided towards any kind of prominent challenges for gender equality, as well as towards any of the aforementioned strategic area.

Strategic area 1: Female Career Progression

Indicative action points

Primary points:

- Set up a quota of female employees in the different positions/departments of R&I organizations (and optional provision of awards for R&I departments that abide by the necessary quota)
- Promotion of gender balance (or gender quota) in decision-making and governance positions and relevant procedures
- Coaching and mentoring programmes for female researchers and entrepreneurs (an emphasis on early-stage researchers and entrepreneurs)
- Digital re-skilling of female employees (e.g. Women Startup Schools, familiarization with new digital working environments)
- Establishment of protocols for: transparent and bias-free recruitment or gender-sensitive recruitment procedures; bias-free promotion procedures; equal allocation of opportunities
- Equal treatment of part-time employees
- Collecting data on gender pay levels on an annual basis, in order to define gender pay gap within the organization
- Policies for facilitating and encouraging the undertaking of high authority positions by females
- Obligatory training on organizational gender issues for HR, recruiting departments and managers in R&I organisations

Strategic area 1: Female Career Progression

Indicative action points

Secondary points:

- Practical actions for supporting young female entrepreneurs (criteria for cooperating with/funding females, cooperating with enterprises with female managers)
- Considering female internal applicants in talent pool before advertising senior positions to external applicants
- Action plans for bridging the gender pay gap, and for having salaries that are aligned to ranks/positions
- Transparency and public provision of data on percentages of female vs. male employees in R&I organizations, as well as of ranks and corresponding salary scales
- Setting targets for equal allocation of R&I funding per gender (mostly relevant for Research Funding Organisations)

Expected outcomes (short-, mid-, long-term)	Individuals and/or organizational departments responsible
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Equal percentages of female and male workforce in core positions and ranks › Higher representation of females in high-authority and decision-making positions › Institutional regulations for bias-free recruitment and promotion procedures, and equal allocation of opportunities › Awarding mechanisms or promotion of the achievement of career milestones by females › Salary scales according to R&I ranks/positions and establishment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Directors (or managers) of R&I organizations › HR and Recruiting departments › Departments of professional development › Departments of personnel support › Career and employability departments

TOOLS

Helpful for Implementation

What works to reduce the gender pay gap - Women's Progression in the Workplace Action Note (City of London – Government Equalities Office)

LIBRA RECRUITMENT HANDBOOK - Inclusive, Transparent and Unbiased Recruitment Processes (LIBRA EU project)

Toolkit for organizing workshops 'precarious positions' for early career researchers (GARCIA EU project)

Change Strategy – Policy brief: Inclusive recruitment and hiring (University of Colorado within the context ADVANCE Programme, funded by National Science Foundation)

Policy Brief 20 – Gender Balance in Decision-making: How to innovate (GENPORT EU project)

Guidelines for Gender Equality programmes in Science – PART D: Women in leadership positions in science and technology (PRAGES EU project)

Factsheet 4 -Best Practice: Promotion (Athena Swan)

Structural change in research institutions: Enhancing excellence, gender equality and efficiency in research and innovation– 4.1 Making decision-making transparent (European Commission)

Gender Equality Policies in Public Research – Section 4: Working Conditions/Recruitment and Career progression (European Commission)

Getting back into research after a career break (Wellcome Trust)

Strategic area 2: Gendered Science

Indicative action points

Primary points:

- Gendering the content of teaching curricula - development of new courses (or components of courses) and curricula that include the gender perspective at all levels of tertiary education
- Training on the use of sex and gender analysis methods in research
- Organisation of informative workshops and seminars on gender in research (mostly in tertiary education and research centres)
- Provision of guidelines or development of a handbook with specifications of the gender-sensitive data collection
- Setting specific criteria for the integration of the gender perspective in funded research programs (applicable to Research Funding Organisations)

Secondary points:

- Making available and endorsing internationally recognized guidelines for improving gender diversity in curricula and research projects, across different disciplines.
- Implementation of a specific institutional policy or strategy that facilitates integrating the gender analysis into the funding programmes for research, including training mechanisms for staff

Expected outcomes (short-, mid-, long-term)	Individuals and/or organizational departments responsible
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › New curricula (or courses/components in courses) integrating the gender perspective › New research projects including sex and gender analysis and the gender perspective › Systematic communication campaigns (e..g trainings, workshops) on gender-aware science and related topics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Deans of academic institutions › Heads of academic Departments › Academic staff › Directors (or managers) of research organizations › Gender Equality Committees

TOOLS

Helpful for Implementation

Toolkit for Integrating Gender Sensitive Approach into Research and Teaching (Garcia EU project)

Research Synthesis 4 - Gender in Research Content and Knowledge Production (GenPORT EU project)

Resources portfolio/toolbox for the implementation of sex, gender & diversity dimension aspects in biomedical research and education (Gendered Innovation Alliance)

Collected good practices in introducing gender in curricula (EGERA EU project)

Manuals with guidelines on the integration of sex and gender analysis into research contents, recommendations for curricula development and indicators (GENDER-NET EU project)

Sex And Gender Equity in Research - SAGER Reporting Guidelines (Gender Policy Committee - European Association of Science Editors)

Gendered Innovations – How gender analysis contributes to Research (European Commission)

IGAR TOOL - Recommendations for Integrating Gender Analysis into Research (GENDER-NET EU project)

Pilot experiences for improving gender equality in research organizations – 5.3 Gender dimension in research and curricula (R&I peers EU project)

EQUAL-IST online toolkit – Gender in Research Content (EQUAL-IST EU project)

Strategic area 3: Confronting Social and Cultural Stereotypes – Challenging Horizontal Segregation

Indicative action points:

Primary points:

- Encouraging female students (and early professionals) towards the STEM field
- Setting targets (quota) for the representation of females in STEM staff positions
- Promoting STEM-oriented funding opportunities to female researchers
- Participation in various EU projects and initiatives aiming to improve gender equality in STEM disciplines and organisations
- Informative, internal/external events towards core concepts where ignorance has been noticed, consequently leading to gender-based stereotypes e.g. distinction between the terms sex and gender
- Designing and implementing campaigns on social and cultural stereotypes, implicit and explicit bias
- Adoption of a working culture that celebrates diversity and rejects all kinds of stereotypes (e.g. equal access to professional resources, including equipment and lab spaces)

Secondary points:

- Promotion of new approaches for motivating young girls towards natural sciences
- Development (or communication) of Manuals on Vocational Guidance for females in all educational and professional grades
- Campaigns for contributing to addressing gendered discrimination from early school years (e.g. gendered discrimination in children's toys and games) that potentially leads to biased educational and professional choices

Expected outcomes (short-, mid-, long-term)	Individuals and/or organizational departments responsible
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Higher female representation in STEM positions in R&I organizations › Higher percentages of females participating (or coordinating) STEM-oriented funded projects › Systematic participation of R&I organizations in EU programmes and initiatives for fostering gender equality in STEM disciplines › Systematic organisation of events and campaigns (internal and external target audience) that a) raise female interest towards STEM disciplines, b) raise awareness on stereotypes and gender bias 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Directors of R&I organizations › Deans of academic institutions › Heads of academic Departments › Marketing and Public Relations departments › Academic staff › Researchers › Career and employability departments › Departments of personnel support › Gender Equality Committees

TOOLS Helpful for Implementation

A Resource Pack for Gender-Responsive STEM Education

Hypatia Toolkit – Gender inclusiveness in science (STEM) teaching

Understanding unconscious bias (Royal society, video) and Unconscious bias briefing

Science Foundation Ireland Gender Strategy – Strand 1: Gender in Education and Public Engagement

Tutorials for Change – Gender Schemas and Science Careers (Hunter College of the City University of New York)

CREATIONS Demonstrators for the STEAM approach (CREATIONS EU project)

Fostering Success for Women in Science and Engineering. Advice for Departmental Faculty: Section 2 Subtle bias and prejudice (University of Wisconsin, ADVANCE programme)

Women in Science and Technology: What Does the Literature Say? – Section 2. Barriers to the Participation of Women in STEM (Inter-American Development Bank)

A Practical Guide to Address GENDER BIAS IN ACADEMIA AND RESEARCH (UNESCO)

‘Advancing Women in STEM’ strategy -2020 Action Plan (Australian Government - Department of Industry, Science, Energy and Resources)

Strategic area 4: Projection of Female Role Models – Appropriate scientific communication

Indicative action points:

Primary points:

- Organisation of site-visits of successful females in R&I e.g lectures seminars in academia and enterprises/companies(synchronous presentation of successful female careers)
- Encouragement of senior academics or senior managers to function as mentors and consequently role models to young female researchers and entrepreneurs (“become an ally and an advocate”)
- Projection of effective good practices of other organizations in the R&I field

Secondary points:

- Projection of video collections including narration of females’ successful professional stories (asynchronous presentation of successful female careers)
- Publication (within the R&I organizations) of magazines/ newsletters including stories of successful female researchers and entrepreneurs
- Projection of effective good practices of other organizations in the R&I field
- Pursuing a fruitful collaboration with European initiatives towards gender and inequality issues –consequently promoting successful initiatives
- Pursuing a fruitful collaboration with NGOs that deal with gender issues and can thus enrich an R&I organisation’s collection of successful stories to be projected

Expected outcomes (short-, mid-, long-term)	Individuals and/or organizational departments responsible
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Establishment of a proper scheme of scientific communication, focusing on regular projection of female role models in R&I › Establishment of (internal) mentoring schemes in R&I organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Directors of R&I organizations › Marketing and Public Relations departments › Departments of professional development › Academic staff › Gender Equality Committees

TOOLS

Helpful for Implementation

Synthesis of gender stereotypes and role-models in STEM education (GENDER4STEM EU project)

Fostering Success for Women in Science and Engineering. Advice for Departmental Faculty: Section 3 Lack of role models and encouragement (University of Wisconsin, ADVANCE programme)

Gender-sensitive Mentoring Programme in Academia: a Design Process – Section 2 What is mentoring? (GARCIA eu project)

EQUAL-IST online toolkit – International networks and conferences (EQUAL-IST EU project)

Working report on gender representation in the audiovisual media sector (Belgian Conseil Supérieur de l'Audiovisuel)

Girls in STEM: Is It a Female Role-Model Thing? (Susana González-Pérez, Ruth Mateos de Cabo and Milagros Sáinz, 2020)

Strategic area 5: Gender-neutral (and/or gender-sensitive) Language in Institutional Communication and Dissemination

Indicative action points

Primary points:

- Training and awareness-raising activities for proper linguistic use of core terms e.g. sex vs. gender, use of generic they instead of he/she, avoidance of exclusionary terms, word ordering etc.
- Creation of official organizational documents with inclusive rather than gender-marked language (or correction of existing documents)
- Promotion and adoption of already existing manuals e.g. “Οδηγός μη σεξιστικής γλώσσας στα διοικητικά έγγραφα» (ΓΕΝΙΚΗ ΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΕΙΑ ΙΣΟΤΗΤΑΣ ΤΩΝ ΦΥΛΩΝ - Γ.Γ.Ι.Φ., EIGE Toolkit on gender sensitive communication)
- Job vacancies with gender-neutral language
- Dissemination activities with a gender-neutral and/or gender-sensitive language
- Promoting language as a carrier of ideologies along with an emphasis on the value of inclusive language

Secondary points:

- Development of organizational protocols on proper language use (in written and verbal communication)
- Generation of lexicons and best practices on communicating in inclusive and non-sexist manner
- Establishment of a department, contact point (email address), or web service where all employees can ask for advice when in doubt concerning matters of communication, and where they can (anonymously) document incidents of gender-biased communication and/or make concrete proposals for improvements

Expected outcomes (short-, mid-, long-term)	Individuals and/or organizational departments responsible
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Institutional regulations regarding gender-sensitive communication and dissemination › Development of an institutional public image (or profile) that is in alignment to core societal concerns and human principles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Directors of R&I organizations › Marketing and Public Relations departments › Human Resources Departments › Heads of Academic Departments › Career and employability departments › Gender Equality Committees

TOOLS

Helpful for Implementation

Οδηγός χρήσης μη σεξιστικής γλώσσας στα διοικητικά έγγραφα

EIGE toolkit on gender sensitive communication

Pilot experiences for improving gender equality in research organizations – 5.5 Gender sensitive language (R&I peers EU project)

Guidelines for using gender-sensitive language in communication, research and administration (Reutlingen University)

EQUAL-IST online toolkit – Section Gender Sensitive Institutional Communication (EQUAL-IST EU project)

Principles for Gender Sensitive Communication (UNDP Gender Equality Seal initiative)

10 principles of gender responsive communications (UNDP – United Nations Development Programme)

Antwerp Charter on gender-sensitive communication in and by academic institutions (EGERA EU project)

Gender Sensitive and Inclusive Language Guide (University of Basel)

United Nations guidelines for gender-sensitive language (United Nations)

Strategic area 6: Work-life Balance

Indicative action points

Primary points:

- Flexible working schemes compatible with family obligations (e.g. options for teleworking/ physical presence blended with teleworking)
- Development of guidelines for accommodating flexible and distance work both for academic and administrative staff with care responsibilities.
- Support mechanisms for parenthood (e.g. extended coverage for maternity leaves, encouragement towards parental leaves, paid adoption leave, prophylactic leave, dual-career measures, providing a period of more flexible working time after return to work)
- Childcare facilities in R&I organizations (e.g. kinder gardens, lactation rooms)
- Further use (after COVID outbreak) of virtual tools fostering higher professional engagement even from the house environment i.e. digital re-skilling
- Promotion and adoption of “work-life balance” action plans by HR departments
- Establishment of a regular review of existent flexible working scheme and other relevant policies
- Provision of training to managers, so as to be able to facilitate and encourage the uptake of flexible work practices
- Reviewing of support processes for staff after returning from parental leave

Strategic area 6: Work-life Balance

Indicative ation points

Secondary points:

- Provision of life coaching seminars on work-life balance (both genders as the audience)
- Introducing a specific 'leave for care scheme' for PhD students as well, within the wider leave of absence
- Supplementary financial support (for research and travel) in light of actual need of students with care responsibilities
- Development of a policy regarding support and options available for staff who are experiencing family or domestic violence
- Development of a comprehensive parenting support information kit

Expected outcomes (short-, mid-, long-term)	Individuals and/or organizational departments responsible
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Establishment of a permanent scheme including regulations for supporting employees' care responsibilities (including institutional regulations on parental leaves) › Establishment of a permanent scheme for teleworking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Directors of R&I organizations › Departments of personnel support › Career and employability departments › Gender Equality Committees

TOOLS Helpful for Implementation

EQUAL-IST online toolkit – HR Management. Work-life balance (EQUAL-IST EU project)

Mapping organisational work-life policies and practices (GARCIA EU project)

Flexible Work Arrangements (University of Colorado within the context ADVANCE Programme)

Fostering Success for Women in Science and Engineering – Section 4. Work-life balance (Advice for Departmental Faculty (University of Wisconsin, ADVANCE programme)

Fact Sheet 2 – Best practice. Work-life balance (Athena Swan)

University of Dundee – Work-life balance (Athena Swan)

Sector-leading and innovative practice in advancing equality and diversity - Section: Maternity leave and career breaks (Equality Challenge Unit – ECU)

Institutional practices and processes – Section Career-life balance (GenPORT EU project)

Supporting work life balance to get more women into ICT (EIGE)

Report on how to improve the research cultural environment - CHAPTER III FLEXIBILITY, TEMPORALITY AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE (GENERA EU project)

Strategic area 7: Sexual Harassment and Gender-based Violence

Indicative action points

Primary points:

- Inclusion of a clear statement against sexual harassment in the institutional mission statement (as well as a clear definition of what is understood by sexual harassment)
- Organizational structures and mechanisms for documentation of related incidents or assaults (i.e. setting up a recording system)
- Establishment of a complaint mechanism - a contact office (or determining a contact person with the appropriate neutrality), where victims or individuals witnessing incidents of sexual harassment can report to (note: ensure anonymity for the witnesses so as to avoid the “bystander effect”)
- Provision of external contact points dealing with sexual harassment and gendered violence (e.g. relevant NGOs and hotlines)
- Development of codes for acceptable behavior within R&I organizations and towards all individuals, irrespective of their gender and their sexual orientation
- Development of an information and resource package for all R&I units on how to handle relevant cases
- Training HR departments and managers of all levels for effectively dealing with incidents of sexual harassment and gendered violence (e.g. quite often the victim rather than the offender is accused)
- Organising internal/external informative events (communication campaigns) on the various forms and manifestations of sexual harassment and gender-based violence

Strategic area 7: Sexual Harassment and Gender-based Violence

Indicative action points

Secondary points:

- Provision of long-term psychological support to victims of sexual harassment and gendered violence, so as to address the long-lingering effects that last beyond the instances the incidents occur (note: if the organisation cannot provide such support, it is advised to refer the victims to relevant experts collaborating with the organisation)
- Encouraging the public announcement of such incidents taking place in R&I organizations (transparency in informing the wider public)
- Organising educational events and programmes on core concepts including consent and respectful relationships
- Creation of 'arenas' and safe spaces for sharing experiences (and raising issues)

Expected outcomes (short-, mid-, long-term)	Individuals and/or organizational departments responsible
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Establishing a permanent scheme addressing sexual harassment and gendered violence in R&I organizations › Enhancing an organizational culture that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ exhibits zero tolerance to sexual harassment and gendered violence ▪ respects and protects core humanitarian principles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Directors of R&I organizations › Deans of academic institutions › HR departments › Gender Equality Committees Staff members in position to undertake relevant initiatives

TOOLS

Helpful for Implementation

Sexism at work: how can we stop it? Handbook for EU institutions and agencies

Hunt, C.M., Davidson, M.J., Fielden, S.L., and Hoel, H. (2010). Reviewing sexual harassment in the workplace – an intervention model. *Personnel Review* 39 (5), 655-673.

Equal Opportunities Commission (EOC) – Preventing and Dealing with Sexual Harassment

Equal Opportunities Commission – Questions and Answers on Preventing Sexual Harassment in Schools

Recommendations to prevent and fight sexual harassment in academia (EGERA EU project)

Guidelines for the prevention of sexual harassment, harassment on grounds of sex and psychological harassment (TRIGGER EU project)

#Science Too: Sexual Harassment in Academic STEM (video by National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, Medicine)

Fostering Success for Women in Science and Engineering. Advice for Departmental Faculty: Section 2 Discrimination and Harassment (University of Wisconsin, ADVANCE programme)

Strategic Framework and Action Plan for Sexual Misconduct, Prevention and Response (The University of Queensland)

RESPECT. NOW. ALWAYS. – A 10-point Action Plan (UNIVERSITIES AUSTRALIA)

Strategic area 8: Raising Awareness on Gender Issues

Indicative action points

Seminars, workshops, training events and communication campaigns can be organized on:

- Any of the aforementioned strategic areas, e.g. on the value of gender-neutral language, on methods for gendering the content and methods of scientific research, on forms and manifestations of sexual harassment etc.
- Greek and EU policies and initiatives on gender equality
- Universal aspirations towards gender equality (e.g. United Nations Sustainable Development Goals)
- Universal principles and notions on equality, gender, inclusiveness, right to diversity, intersectionality, diversity management and implicit prejudice (bias)

Expected outcomes (short-, mid-, long-term)	Individuals and/or organizational departments responsible
<ul style="list-style-type: none">› Institutional awareness on gender and equality principles, as well as on diversity rights› A new organizational culture and image, based on core humanitarian principles	<ul style="list-style-type: none">› Directors of R&I organizations› Deans of academic departments› Heads of Departments› HR departments› Marketing and Public Relations departments› Gender Equality Committees› Staff members in position to undertake relevant initiatives

4

Suggesting Monitoring and Evaluation Frameworks

- 4.1 General suggestions for monitoring and evaluating a GEP
- 4.2 Monitoring indicators
- 4.3 Gender-sensitive evaluation criteria and evaluative questions

The implementation of a GEP should be accompanied by an appropriate scheme for data collection, monitoring and evaluation of its progress. These processes actually encompass a systematic and objective assessment of the implementation and results of the GEP –or the results of any other activity from a gender perspective. Monitoring and evaluation tasks take into account the information and data collected and collated in the course of different implementation phases of the GEP, as well as other knowledge and sources. These tasks are also accompanied by various monitoring indicators and evaluation criteria.

It should be highlighted that monitoring/evaluation criteria and indicators need to be formed separately (be self-tailored) for each organisation implementing a GEP –since particularly the indicators need to be formed in accordance to the action points adopted and the gender-related initiatives to be implemented. The sections below provide details on some indicative monitoring/evaluation frameworks, indicators and criteria that GEP implementing organisations can adopt for ‘assessing’ their GEP’s progress.

The present chapter is thus structured in various sub-sections. Firstly, sub-section 4.1 provides some general guidelines and suggestions for applying a successful and effective monitoring and evaluation approach. Afterwards, a list with potentially useful monitoring indicators –in correspondence to the strategic areas of chapter 3– is outlined (section 4.2), followed by some indicative evaluation criteria and evaluative questions (section 4.3).

4.1 General suggestions for monitoring and evaluating a GEP

Monitoring and evaluation can be seen as a part of the process of change for the organisation implementing the GEP. The gender-sensitive monitoring is a systematic and objective assessment of the design and planning (objectives, results pursued, activities planned), the implementation and results of an ongoing activity, project, programme or policy. Monitoring exercises occur periodically and are aimed at following up the implementation of a policy or a programme. This includes data collection and information based on the defined gender equality objectives and indicators, in order to verify whether the plan is being followed and whether the objectives are being achieved. Notably, it functions like ‘an early warning system’, which indicates potential problems towards goal achievement and ideas for remedial activities (Woodhouse, Howlett & Rigby, 2000).

The gender-sensitive evaluation has similar objectives to the monitoring. It should primarily be highlighted that evaluation can take place upon the completion of a specific/determined time frame (e.g. annually, bi-annually), when the focus is placed on gender impacts and the contribution of the plan to promoting gender equality. In similar lines, it takes place throughout the GEP implementation, with the aim of achieving a continuous improvement. It can finally take place ex ante, in order to evaluate how a policy can affect gender equality in a specific field.

According to EIGE, some general suggestions towards both monitoring and evaluating a GEP are the following:

- The best way to capture the status of gender (in-)equality in the organisation and to assess progress is by combining the use of quantitative indicators with qualitative ones. Gender-sensitive and gender-specific indicators contribute to measuring gender-related changes over time. They can be quantitative (e.g. number of female and male researchers), or qualitative (usually used to capture/assess people's experiences, opinions, attitudes, behaviours, feelings). While quantitative indicators can provide statistical evidence of what has changed, qualitative analyses allow assessing the quality of change and help understanding why certain patterns have occurred.
- 'Women' and 'men' are no monolithic groups, and differences in the situations of individuals within these groups might be bigger than between the groups. Attention for intersecting inequalities and the influence of other factors (intersectionality), including age, race, family status, contractual basis etc., is thus warranted.
- While implementing a GEP in R&I organisations, different areas and themes can be addressed through specific initiatives. For each thematic/strategic area, a range of corresponding activities and instruments can be mobilized for monitoring/evaluating.
- Ex-ante evaluation can prove to be valuable. GEPs are better designed if relying upon a comprehensive assessment of the status of gender equality. This assessment can take different forms. An audit can be carried out with the support of external and impartial expertise. Internal knowledge about gender and the institution itself can also be mobilised. Different tools can be used for investigating gender inequalities, bias and imbalances at all levels, including pilot studies, surveys, focus groups, interviews or ethnographic observation.

4.2 Monitoring indicators

An indicator is a measurable variable that helps assess the current situation and track change over a period of time. The present sub-section firstly clarifies what is meant by quantitative and qualitative indicators, which are often employed by organisations implementing the GEPs (Figure 2). Indicators need to be adapted by each organisation, in correspondence to the gender-related action points they are implementing. Tables 3.a-3.i exemplify some specific indicators, in relation to the specific strategic areas addressed in the RCM GEP. These indicators have been adapted from previous EU projects, from previous (university-level) GEPs, or they have been formed by the Authority of RCM and SEERC team in correspondence to the strategic areas suggested in chapter 3. Therefore, these indicators can potentially function as a basis and/or as an inspiration point for the organisations of RCM and the self-tailored indicators they will wish to employ throughout their GEPs.

Figure 2. General description of qualitative and quantitative indicators

The catalogue depicted in Tables 3.a-3.i includes specific quantitative and qualitative indicators that can be employed for assessing the progress of self-tailored Gender Equality Plans/GEPs. These indicators are separated per strategic area they address (in accordance to the strategic areas indicated in chapter 3 of this document). The column “Monitoring Indicators” describes the suggested indicator and a parenthesis indicates whether it is a quantitative (QN) or qualitative indicator (QL). The column “Target values” describes what kind of targets the R&I organisations could set with reference to each indicator (the exact target value shall of course be set by the organisations themselves, depending on aims, gaps, structures, internal mechanisms etc.).

FEMALE CAREER PROGRESSION

(INCLUDING GOVERNANCE BODIES, DECISION-MAKING PROCEDURES AND POSITIONS)

Monitoring Indicators	Target values (set up by the institutions)
Representation of men and women in the main/highest governing bodies of the institution (QN)	X% of the members in the main/highest governing bodies are females
Representation of men and women in the main/highest advisory bodies of the institution (QN)	X% of the members in the main/highest advisory bodies are females
Representation of women and men at other high-authority (leadership) positions (QN)	X% of the individuals holding high-authority (leadership) positions are females
Career Support Schemes (QL/QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a career support scheme in the organisation • X number of new career support schemes in the R&I organisation • Equal share of women and men participating at the career support schemes
Protocols/Schemes for transparent, bias-free and/or gender-sensitive recruitment (QL/QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a scheme for transparent, bias-free and/or gender-sensitive recruitment • X number of new schemes and/or protocols for ensuring fair and transparent recruitment
Gender diversity on selection panels for recruitment (QN)	X% of the members in the selection panels are females
Mentoring schemes and/or initiatives for female employees (QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X number of existent (or new) mentoring schemes and/or initiatives for female employees

Share of funded and coordinated projects per gender (QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X number of projects coordinated by women • Increased number (X%) of the share of women coordinators in European and national R&I funded projects
Ratio of female starting salaries vs. male starting salaries (for the same ranks and positions) (QN)	Equal starting salaries per gender for the same ranks and positions
Gender pay gap per rank X	Decreased number (%) of gender pay gap in rank X
Pay equity reports (QL)	Pay equity reports are submitted (e.g. annually)
Contract conditions (part time/full time, duration of contracts) per gender (QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Similar percentage of females and males having part-time contracts • Similar percentage of females and males having full-time contracts (or X% of females having full time contracts)
Ratification of the European Charter for Researchers (QL)	The European Charter for Researchers is ratified by the R&I organisation
Number of scientific papers (publications) including sex/gender variables and dimensions (QN)	Increased number (%) of scientific papers including sex/gender variables and dimensions in total
Number of funded projects with gender aspects (QN)	Increased number (%) of funded projects that include gender aspects and the R&I organisation participates to.

Table 3.a. Female Career Progression

GENDERED SCIENCE

Monitoring Indicators	Target values (set up by the institutions)
Number of courses with gender aspects (QN)	Increased number (%) of courses that include gender aspects
Training schemes for sex and gender analysis methods in research, as well as on gender-sensitive data collection (QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X number of existent (or new) training schemes (e.g., workshops, events) • Equal share of women and men participating at the training • Increased number (X%) of attendees over time
Informational events on gender in research (QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X number of relevant events • Equal share of women and men participating at the events • Increased number (X%) of attendees over time

Table 3.b. Gendered Science

CONFRONTING SOCIAL AND CULTURAL STEREOTYPES – CHALLENGING HORIZONTAL SEGREGATION

Monitoring Indicators	Target values (set up by the institutions)
Initiatives for internally raising awareness on gender-related social and cultural stereotypes (QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X number of relevant initiatives (or increased number (X%) of relevant initiatives) • Equal share of women and men participating at the events • Increased number (X%) of participants over time
Representation of men and women in STEM-related positions (QN)	X% of the individuals holding STEM-related positions are females
Coordination of STEM-oriented funded projects per gender	Increased number (X%) of the share of women coordinators in European and national STEM-oriented funded projects

Table 3.c. Confronting social and cultural stereotypes - Challenging Horizontal segregation

PROJECTION OF FEMALE ROLE MODELS – APPROPRIATE SCIENTIFIC COMMUNICATION

Monitoring Indicators	Target values (set up by the institutions)
Initiatives for raising awareness on female role models (QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X number of relevant initiatives or increased number (X%) of relevant initiatives • Increased number (X%) of participants over time
Gender sensitive language and images in institutional documents (If there is such a policy, the indicators monitor its implementation) (QN).	Increased Number (X%) of institutional documents using gender sensitive language (written and visual)

Table 3.d. Projection of female role models - Appropriate scientific communication

GENDER-NEUTRAL (OR GENDER-SENSITIVE) LANGUAGE IN INSTITUTIONAL COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

Monitoring Indicators	Target values (set up by the institutions)
Gender neutral and/or gender sensitive language in employment vacancies and advertisements (QN).	Increased Number (X%) of vacancies and advertisements using gender neutral or gender sensitive language
Protocols for appropriate language use and communication (internal and external) (QN)	X number of existent (or new) protocols for appropriate internal and external language use and communication
Staffs' perception towards the value of gender-neutral and/or sensitive language (QL)	Staff members have a positive opinion towards the value of gender-neutral and/or sensitive language towards achieving equality in their organisation

Table 3.e. Gender-neutral (or gender-sensitive) language in institutional communication and dissemination

WORK-LIFE BALANCE

Monitoring Indicators	Target values (set up by the institutions)
Provision of services for work and personal life integration (QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased number (%) of work and personal life integration services (e.g., service for dual career couples, scheme for teleworking, teaching relief support scheme for new parents so that returners don't fall further behind in research and career paths) X number of (female) employees taking advantage of work and personal life integration services
Demand and supply of basic child care (QN)	Decreased (X%) gap between demand and supply of nurseries and kindergartens (or other childcare facilities in the R&I organisation)
Standard procedure for parental leave (QL/QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existence of a standard procedure for parental leave (QL) Increased (X%) percentage of men taking parental leaves (QN)
Training scheme (related to work-life balance) for HR managers (QL)	Existence of a training scheme for HR managers
Support scheme for employees-victims of family and domestic violence (QL)	Existence of a support scheme for victims of family and domestic violence
Guidelines for accommodating flexible and distance work (addressing staff with care responsibilities) (QL)	Existence of guidelines for accommodating flexible and distance work
Staff's perception towards the existence of work-life balance (QL)	Staff members have a positive opinion towards the facilitation of their work-life balance on behalf of their organization

Table 3.f. Work-life-balance

SEXUAL HARASSMENT AND GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

Monitoring Indicators	Target values (set up by the institutions)
Staff awareness of harassment manifestations (QL)	Staff members are adequately aware of what it means to be sexually harassed
Initiatives/events for raising awareness on sexual harassment and gender-based violence (QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X number of relevant initiatives (or increased number (X%) of relevant initiatives) • Equal share of women and men participating at the events • Increased number (X%) of participants over time
Training scheme for HR managers and directors of R&I organisations (QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X number of existent or new training schemes
Contact point for victims of harassment and gender-based violence (QL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existence of a contact point inside the R&I organisation
Recording system for the documentation of relevant incidents (QL)	Existence of a recording system
Psychological support units (QL)	Existence of units providing psychological support to victims of harassment and violent, gender-related incidents
Protocol/code of conduct of proper behavior towards all individuals, irrespective of gender, sexual orientation etc. (QL)	Existence of such a protocol/code of conduct in the R&I organisation

Table 3.g. Sexual harassment and gender-based violence

RAISING AWARENESS ON GENDER ISSUES

Monitoring Indicators	Target values (set up by the institutions)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness-raising events (particular emphasis on unconscious bias) and training on gender sensitive issues (internal: addressing recruitment selection committees, HR departments, decision-makers and public communication officers) (QN) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X number of internal awareness-raising events and training on gender issues Increased (X%) number of attendees over time
<p>Awareness-raising events and training on gender sensitive issues (external: addressing the lay public) (QN)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X number of external awareness-raising events and training on gender issues Increased (X%) number of attendees over time

Table 3.h. Raising awareness on gender issues

GENERAL (WITH REFERENCE TO THE STRUCTURES AND HOLISTIC ACTIVITIES OF THE R&I ORGANISATION)

Monitoring Indicators	Target values (set up by the institutions)
Provision of gender disaggregated data in RPO's periodic report (QL)	Periodic reports are released with gender disaggregated data
Public mission statement of the R&I organisation towards gender equality (QL)	Existence of a public document (formal, signed by top management) published on the institution's website, referring to the organisation's enhancement of gender equality
Meetings for GEPs implementation (QN)	X number of regular meetings for monitoring and assessing the GEP's implementation
Staff's perception towards the gender equality aspects in the organisation's policies (QL/QN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Staff members have a positive opinion towards the relevance and efficiency of the gender equality policies of their organisation (QL) Increase (X%) of staff members in the R&I organisation, who believe policies on gender equality are relevant and effective in their organisation (QN)
Inclusion of gender issues in the organisation's induction process (QL)	All newly recruited staff should go through an induction process, making them aware of the organisation's gender related policies and services

Table 3.i. General (in reference to the structures and holistic activities of the R&I organisation)

Note

Once the indicators have been selected, baseline information should be collected to provide a reference point to measure changes that take place over time in the respective intervention. This can be very useful in benchmarking and mapping progress over time. Data collected on gender indicators can be assessed against the agreed outcomes to examine whether the intervention triggered the expected changes in women's and men's situations.

TOOLS

Helpful for Implementation

The set of PLOTINA indicators (PLOTINA EU project)

Tool Kit on Gender Equality Results and Indicators (by Australian Aid and the Asian Development Bank)

Updated handbook of gender-sensitive indicators in the Baltic Gender project (by Baltic Gender EU project)

Mapping of Tools for the Evaluation of Gender Equality Plans (by SAGE project)

FESTA toolkit Towards Raising Organizational Awareness (by FESTA EU project)

4.3 Gender-sensitive evaluation criteria and evaluative questions

According to EIGE, widely used evaluation criteria for a GEP are: relevance, efficiency, effectiveness, impact and sustainability:

- **Relevance:** Has the GEP effectively contributed to the creation of favourable conditions for gender equality? Did it respond to the practical and strategic gender needs of women? Did it contribute to the national and EU policy commitments and mandates regarding gender equality? Was the treatment of gender equality issues throughout the implementation phase logical and coherent? Were adjustments made to respond to external factors of the project/programme (e.g. economic crisis, new government etc.) which influenced gender relationships?
- **Efficiency:** Has the implementation of the GEP been efficient with respect to gender equality? Are the means and resources being used efficiently to achieve results in terms of improved benefits for both women and men? Have the results for women and men been achieved at reasonable cost, and have costs and benefits been allocated and received equitably?
- **Effectiveness:** Did the GEP results turn out to be effective in achieving gender equality? Have the results contributed to the achievement of the planned results and outcomes, and have benefits favoured male and/or female target groups? Did stakeholders (organisations, institutions, indirect target groups) benefit from the interventions in terms of institutional capacity-building in the area of gender mainstreaming and the development of gender competence among their staff?

- **Impact:** What has been the impact of the GEP's outcomes on wider policies, processes and programmes which enhance gender equality and women's rights? For example, did it have an impact on reducing violence against women? Did it contribute to a more balanced distribution of unpaid care labour and family responsibilities between women and men?
- **Sustainability:** Are achievements in gender equality likely to be sustained after the specific time period set for the GEP ends? To what extent has ownership of the policy goals been achieved by male and female beneficiaries? To what extent have strategic gender needs of women and men been addressed through the GEP, and has this resulted in sustainable improvement of women's rights and gender equality? To what extent has, through the GEP, the capacity for gender been built and institutionalised?

A few sample evaluation questions on gender equality are also displayed in relevant toolkits provided by OECD (e.g. toolkit on Gender Equality Results and Indicators by the Asian Development Bank and Australian Aid). After adapted, these questions can be applied within the context of GEPs' implementation. In more details:

Gender Capacity building

- Are sex-disaggregated data regularly collected and analyzed? Has gender analysis skills been strengthened within the organisation, including its capacity to develop, implement, and monitor gender strategies? Is there a greater understanding of gender issues in the organisation and of the most effective strategies to address women's needs and priorities, as well as those of men?

Lessons Learned about Constraints, Strategies, and Sustainability

- What factors and strategies helped to foster positive changes toward gender equality? What constrained the achievement of equal participation, benefits, and outcomes for females?
- Were there any initiatives (or components of the initiatives) where males benefited much more than females? If yes, what contributed to this?
- Were there any unintended positive or negative changes in gender relations? What factors and strategies contributed to these changes?
- Are positive changes in gender relations in the organisation likely to be sustained? What factors will contribute to this, and what is likely to undermine the sustainability of positive changes?
- What further changes need to be made to enhance progress toward gender equality in the organisation?

5

Indicative new organizational structures
(supporting GEP implementation)

Each organization implementing a GEP can further enhance its effectiveness by new and relevant organizational structures, potentially functioning as sustainability mechanisms. In accordance to the strategic areas addressed and to the action points to be implemented, new organizational structures can refer to the following:

- Gender Equality Committees (particularly in HEIs)
- GEP working groups/Equality Officers (also indicated by the funding programme of Horizon Europe as a necessary building-block of GEPs)
- Monitoring and evaluation teams
- Complaint office (contact point) for victims of sexual harassment and gender-based violence
- Psychological support units for victims of sexual harassment and gender-based violence
- Consultation units, providing 'life coaching' on the reconciliation of work and personal life
- Mentoring teams/groups for females working at the organisations and being at the early stage of their careers.

Further resources

EU projects resources

- GENDER-NET D3.11: Manuals with guidelines on the integration of sex and gender analysis into research contents, recommendations for curricula development and indicators
- EQUAL-IST online toolkit for designing and implementing GEPs in ICT/IST research institutions
- TARGET EU project – Σχέδια Δράσης για την Ισότητα των Φύλων σε Πανεπιστήμια και Οργανισμούς Έρευνας: Κατευθυντήριες Γραμμές και Εργαλεία
- RRI practice EU project - policy recommendations to European policy makers on Gender
- Hypatia Institutional Guidelines - How to make your organisation more gender inclusive

EU sources on gender mainstreaming

- European Institute of Gender Equality (EIGE)
- She figures 2018
- She Figures 2015
- Gender Statistics database: women and men in decision-making
- Gender Statistics database: gender-based violence
- A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 (Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, European Economic and Social Committee, Committee of the Regions)
- Gender Policy Committee (GPC) of the European Association of Science Editors

- White Ribbon Campaign: Changing Violence against women
- Gender Equality Index 2020 - GREECE
- Gender Equality in Academia and Research – GEAR tool
- Science Europe: Practical Guide to Improving Gender Equality in Research Organisations
- Guidance to facilitate the implementation of targets to promote gender equality in research and innovation (European Commission) LAW No. 4604 for Promoting Substantive Gender Equality (Hellenic Republic)

Greek sources on gender mainstreaming

- LAW No. 4604 for Promoting Substantive Gender Equality (Hellenic Republic)
- Εθνικό Σχέδιο Δράσης για την Ισότητα των Φύλων 2016 – 2020 (General Secretariat for Gender Equality)
- Η συμμετοχή των γυναικών στην Έρευνα & Ανάπτυξη στην Ελλάδα (Έκδοση 2020, Εθνικό Κέντρο Τεκμηρίωσης)
- Κείμενο πολιτικής: Η ισότητα των φύλων στη μεταρρύθμιση για την Ανώτατη Εκπαίδευση στην Ελλάδα (ΕΛΙΑΜΕΠ)

Other

- Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): Goal 5 – Gender Equality (United Nations)
- Unicef – Gender Equality

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